

Effective Pedagogies for Online Teaching and Learning

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Introduction

The research on effective pedagogies and online learning points to the continual increases of online distance students and programs in the United States (Allen & Seaman, 2008; 2016; 2018; Budhai & Williams, 2016; Keengwe & Kidd, 2010). In 2008, there were 3.9 million online distance students, in 2014 the number went up to 5.1 million, and in 2016 it grew to 6.3 million (Allen & Seaman, 2008; 2016; 2018). According to Keengwe and Kidd (2010) these statistical figures are impacting college and university professors where many have been asked to begin a transition to online classrooms. It is widely known that online teaching and learning differs from traditional teaching and learning. Many experts believe a constructivist and andragogical approach must be embraced in order to successfully teach and learn in online environments (Goddu, 2012; Pelz, 2010; Adebisi & Oyeleke, 2018; Budhai & Williams, 2016; Campbell, 2004; Keengwe & Kidd, 2010).

In their research on effective strategies for online environments Adebisi and Oyeleke (2018) suggest the constructivist theory as the key element for effective teaching. They describe it as a theory, which focuses on collaboration between faculty and students in the learning process. Students become active participants, and professors facilitate an environment for learning and growth. Campbell (2004), as cited by Keengwe and Kidd (2010), also stated that online learning is more about metacognitive, reflective, collaborative, and student's self-directed learning. Additionally, Goddu (2012) presented two fundamental models of adult learning theory. First Piaget's (1972), foundational theory of adult learning, which emphasizes the value of adult learners in constructing knowledge and cognition. The second model is Knowles' (1977) andragogy theory, which focuses on the singularities of adult learners, the experiences they bring to the classroom, the motivational elements for adult learners, and the way they learn. Adebisi and Oyeleke (2018) believe it is important to recognize the value of andragogical principles for online learning. Citing sections of Knowles (1973; 1980; 1984) andragogy theory of adult learning, where the self-actualization of the individual is the center point of instructional practice. Knowles andragogical assumptions, for example, show the differences between each model; (1) adult's self-concept, from being dependent and directed to being independent and self-directed; (2) adult's experiences, past experiences are seen as a source of knowledge; (3) adult's readiness to learn, learning must be meaningful and connected to roles; (4) adult's orientation to learning, learning must be relevant and applicable to tasks or goals; and finally (5) adult's motivation to learn, the intrinsic personal motivation for learning. This model sees faculty as facilitators or consultants rather than lecturers.

Most Effective Pedagogies According to Experts

Online learning must be transformative (Budhai & Williams, 2016). In online learning, students do most of the work; professors talk less, provide less lecture time but listen or read more of student led discussions (Pelz, 2010). In the words of Adebisi and Oyeleke (2018), "effective teaching strategies help activate students' curiosity about a class topic, engage students in learning, develop critical learning skills, keep students on task, engender sustained and useful classroom interaction, and in general, enable and enhance the learning of course content" (p. 168). The following

framework presents four main areas of attention for successful online teaching. These came after analyzing the literature, and building upon the research of Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2000) on the Community of Inquiry Model. Budhai and Williams (2016) believe this model to be one of the top pedagogies for online learning, where there is a focus on teaching, social, and cognitive presence. However, this model lacks the inclusion of the technical/managerial presence, which the literature shows is also important for online teaching (Keengwe & Kidd, 2010; Berger, 1995; Adebisi & Oyeleke, 2018; Bjekic, Krneta & Milosevic, 2010; Coppola, Hiltz & Rotter, 2002).

Technical/Managerial Presence

This significant addition to Garrison, Anderson and Archer's Community of Inquiry Model is important because according to Keengwe and Kidd (2010) online faculty are viewed in multiple perspectives, one of those perspectives being a predisposition to embrace a technical and managerial presence. A technical managerial presence is an area conducive to learning and using technical skills, instructional design, and content management or development for online teaching. Coppola, Hiltz, and Rotter (2002) also consider managerial skills as one of the main roles for faculty in online environments. Additional researchers consider technical and managerial aspects very valuable for online teaching (Bjekic, Krneta & Milosevic, 2010; Adebisi & Oyeleke, 2018; Berger, 1995). Technical/managerial presence has to do with the ownership of the course design and content, thus with the course outcomes. It is being present as the one responsible for the learning process through the technology and the strategic management of course content.

Teaching Presence

According to Budhai and Williams (2016) it is the task of facilitating, designing, and guiding the learning process. The professors are cognizant of the course organization and the systematic organization of content, for example, weekly videos, assignments, readings, discussion boards, etc. The use of direct instruction as instructors develop short but substantial video content and engage purposely in the discussion forums are the opportunities to be present and share their knowledge and insight. Moreover, for substantial learning to take place instructors could utilize direct instruction to increase teaching presence by a) presenting content and questions, b) focusing the discussion, c) summarizing the discussion, d) confirming understanding, e) diagnosing misconceptions, f) injecting knowledge from diverse sources, and g) responding to technical concerns (Pelz, 2010). Teaching presence has to do with the level of engagement and participation of the professors in the strategic design and outcomes of the course. It is being present as the one responsible for the learning process through the alignment of course material and the personal commitment to participate.

Social Presence

Coppola, Hiltz, and Rotter (2002) asserted that one of the main roles of instructors in online learning environments is being affective. Social presence is the task of building camaraderie and community in online classrooms. Instructors should help develop course content that will engage the students in cohesive relationships and community with other students in the group (Pelz, 2010). The goal for instructors would be to encourage collaboration and promote the development of a community of learners that support each other and bolsters social engagement (Keengwe & Kidd, 2010; Adebisi & Oyeleke, 2018). Social presence has to do with the socio relational aspects of the online classroom and the connectivity and encouragement of the professors. It is being present as

the one responsible for the social engagement through the use of course activities and the intentional encouragement of a cohesive environment.

Cognitive Presence

It is the learning environment strategically designed by instructors and conducive to meaningful learning. Instructors develop rich discussion questions and help the students connect factual, conceptual, and theoretical content (Pelz, 2010). The weekly course content is carefully assessed to make sure it activates cognitive processes and deep learning (Coppola, Hiltz & Rotter, 2002). Furthermore, professors are the architects that facilitate discourse; the weekly discussion questions should be designed to promote deeper level thinking and meaningful learning. Interconnectivity and alignment of the weekly content and questions is very important (Budhai & Williams, 2016). Cognitive presence has to do with the level of precision and quality of the weekly discussion questions and the conversations that are generated during the course. It is being present as the one responsible for the cognitive processes of students through the careful formulation of questions.

Practical Implications for Online Faculty

The following are two practical implications drawn from this research:

Prepares Course Content Well

A major role of the online professor is the development of relevant and effective course material and weekly content. For example, if you spend three hours a week teaching a traditional course and another three or more preparing each week then you should commit six hours a week to compensate and make sure you are preparing and presenting substantial content (Price, Whitlatch, Maier, Burdi & Peacock, 2016). Using that time for course creation and preparing updated weekly videos, teaching, engaging in the weekly forums and staying up to date with the research in the subject are some of the activities an online faculty member should be involved in on a weekly basis depending on the amount of courses he or she may be teaching (Keengwe & Kidd, 2010; Adebisi & Oyeleke, 2018). Students will notice if you are not prepared for the week, because in online environments, the content of the week must be ready for the students to be able to engage with the material. If you prepare well for the course, your students will learn more and engage more. Online teaching requires a proactive approach to course design and weekly engagement in order to provide the best quality of instruction.

Serves Students Well

Part of the work of a professor is to build relationships with the students where there could be learning and proper communication of expectations and subject matter. In online formats, faculty must become proactive at reaching out to students and communicating constantly in order to help them stay on task and on track. Pelz (2010) believes that interactivity is the heart and soul of online learning, the weekly discussions between students, with the input of the professors is very positive. For professor Pelz, the online environment creates an opportunity for all students to participate by reading and writing, which for him this is even better for academic learning than a traditional class discussion. Others such as Price, Whitlatch, Maier, Burdi and Peacock (2016) also suggest good and timely communication with students as a fundamental skill for online teaching. This will require a commitment to frequent communication and interaction with students (Keengwe & Kidd, 2010).

Conclusion

In order to understand online education and explore effective teaching pedagogies, we need to reflect upon these foundational theories and perhaps conclude that online teaching and learning are in fact different, but at the same time both are proven to work. It is clear that everyone has the ability to learn proper knowledge and skills for effective online teaching. If the professor would focus on the four areas presented here; technical/managerial presence, teaching presence, cognitive presence, and social presence, they would not only learn how to become great online professors, but they would also become better at evaluating and assessing student learning outcomes and their teaching content. The numbers do not lie, as online distance programs and students continue to grow, the present reality is that sooner or later the demand for more online professors will continue to increase. One last thought, as educational leaders we are always teaching our students to become life-long learners. The new online educational environment of today requires that we become those life-long learners that are acquainted with the new pedagogies for online teaching and the new technology required for facilitating online instruction (Adebisi & Oyeleke, 2018; Keengwe & Kidd, 2010).

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